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Abstract. *This article analyzes the impact of demographic transformations in the Fergana Valley on interethnic relations, population dynamics and changes in the national composition.*

Key words: *national cultural center, demography, population, national composition, tolerance.*

ИЗМЕНЕНИЕ ДЕМОГРАФИЧЕСКОЙ СИТУАЦИИ МЕЖНАЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ОТНОШЕНИЯ

Аннотация. *В этой статье анализируются влияние демографических преобразований в Ферганской долине на межэтнические отношения, динамику населения и изменения в национальном составе.*

Ключевые слова: *национально-культурный центр, демография, население, национальный состав, толерантность.*

INTRODUCTION

Peace, tranquility, friendship and solidarity between peoples have always been one of the main factors determining the development of any state and its future. Therefore, since the early years of independence, our country has been paying special attention to the preservation of values of different nationalities, creating the necessary conditions for all citizens to practice their faith, further strengthening interethnic harmony and developing ancient common traditions. Article 18 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that "In the Republic of Uzbekistan, all citizens have the same rights and freedoms and are equal before the law, regardless of gender, race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, creed, personal and social status." marked as This serves to strengthen the harmony and solidarity between our multinational peoples, to further expand the modern demographic and transformation processes formed in independent Uzbekistan. Interethnic harmony and religious tolerance, which are ingrained in the blood of our people, have further developed during the years of independence, its legal basis has been created and has a strong place in national policy. This policy, as well as the basis of the national idea, can be clearly seen in the lives of people of different nationalities living in one society and working towards a common goal.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

As the population gradually grows in accordance with the laws of economic and social life, demographic processes also develop depending on the particular mode of production and the relation of production. Population is a product of complex social and natural development, which is influenced by various factors. In this respect, it is close to the topic of analysis of economics, sociology, geography, medicine, historical sciences, and uses their achievements, while providing them with important information.

Socio-economic development plays a key role in the formation of demographic processes. Improvement of living standards, improvement of the quality of medical services has

a positive impact on demographic processes and leads to population growth, while wars, various diseases, economic crises, famines and other factors have a negative impact on demographic processes. Demographic processes are the course of events in people's lives that are associated with the change of their generations [2]. Demographic processes in the years of independence in the Republic of Uzbekistan differ from other periods by their specificity. The fact that the average life expectancy of the population of the republic has increased from 67 to 73.8 years in the last twenty years is a testament to many things [3]. In particular, life expectancy for women was 76.2 years and for men 71.4 years [4].

Uzbekistan's transition to the path of independent development marked a new stage in its demographic history. As a result of the formation of market relations, changes in socio-economic and political conditions in the country, new demographic changes have occurred. This, in turn, has affected the interethnic relations of our multinational republic.

In 1991, the population of the republic was 20,607.7 thousand [5], but as of April 1, 2019, this figure exceeded 33.3 million people [6]. From the first days of independence, the state policy of interethnic harmony and tolerance has been pursued. This policy creates a wide range of conditions for people of different nationalities to live freely in Uzbekistan. This can be seen in the establishment of the Republican International Cultural Center by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 13, 1992 [7].

RESULTS

To further strengthen the principles of a healthy lifestyle, interethnic harmony, mutual love and interreligious tolerance in society, to preserve and pass on the ancient traditions of our multinational people to future generations, to instill in the hearts and minds of the younger generation love for the motherland and independence. The work carried out to coordinate and further develop the activities of national-cultural centers in the regions of the Fergana Valley is bearing fruit [8]. In particular, the leadership of Andijan region has established 5 national cultural centers in the region, in particular, Uyghur, Korean, Armenian, Kyrgyz and Russian, taking into account the need of the times to meet national needs. These centers play an important role in strengthening friendship, peace and tranquility in our society. One of these national-cultural centers is the Uyghur Cultural Center in Uzbekistan. It was one of the first national cultural centers established in Uzbekistan in 1989. The center has set itself the task of holding cultural and educational events in accordance with the work plan to provide comprehensive support to the Uighur population in the region, the preservation of national values, language and culture. Accordingly, at the initiative of the Republican and regional Uyghur National Cultural Center, many spiritual and educational events have been held under the motto "Our Common Home of Uzbekistan."

The 1990s were an important period in the activities of the Uyghur Cultural Center in Andijan, which played an important role in the preservation and development of national culture, customs and traditions. During this period, the Uyghur diaspora gained its place among the national and cultural centers of the country. In Pakhtaabad district of Andijan region there is a regional branch of the center [9].

During the years of independence, the Uyghurs in the Fergana Valley have been actively involved in agriculture as part of socio-economic changes. For example, in the Uyghur village

assembly in Pakhtaabad district of Andijan region, 29 farms operating in various fields are headed by Uyghur citizens [10].

By 1991, the center began to actively promote the restoration of language, history, traditions and customs on the basis of universal values for the enrichment of national culture in order to further develop interethnic relations. The center has set itself the task of a wide range of events and programs. Of the center's 5,000 members, 2,450 are under the age of 30, of whom more than 1,000 are women. The number of team members in the center is 10 sectors. The largest number of members is the population of the collective farm named after Olim Kurbanov of Pakhtaabad district. As of December 24, 2005, the population of the Uyghur diaspora was 18,591. About 12,500 of them are under 30 years old. Currently, the population of the Uyghur diaspora is 24,000. Of these, 60 people are involved in the center. The most densely populated areas of the Uyghur diaspora in Andijan are Pakhtaabad, Shahrikhan, Kurgantepa, Asaka districts and the city of Andijan.

Every year, district and city departments take an active part in the Independence Day celebrations. The center hosts evenings and anniversaries dedicated to the anniversaries and works of Uyghur artists, community members and workers. During the years of independence, the Uyghur diaspora has become an association that contributes to the socio-economic development of Uzbekistan, while preserving its national culture and traditions.

Founded in 1995, the Kyrgyz Diaspora was registered by the regional Department of Justice on June 7, 1996 with Certificate No. 63. In Andijan, the most densely populated areas of the Kyrgyz diaspora are Bulakbashi, Khojaabad, Jalal-Abad, Kurgantepa, Marhamat, Pakhtaabad districts, Karasuv and Khanabad, which border Kyrgyzstan, and enjoy full political, economic and social rights under the Constitution. Currently, there are 33 Kyrgyz-language secondary schools in Andijan region, including 9 Kyrgyz and 24 Uzbek-Kyrgyz language schools [12], as well as a specialized boarding school with a single Kyrgyz language of instruction. The regional television and radio company broadcasts in Kyrgyz. In addition, the Faculty of Philology of Andijan State University has a department of Kyrgyz language and literature, which trains specialists to teach in Kyrgyz. In addition, in the 1998-1999 academic year, 371 Kyrgyz high school graduates from Andijan region were sent to study at universities in Osh and Jalal-Abad regions of Kyrgyzstan. This is a testament to the care for people of different nationalities living in our country and the establishment of social justice.

By 2000, Uzbeks accounted for 88.8 percent of the region's ethnic population and Kyrgyz for 3.8 percent. By 2005, Andijan had a Kyrgyz ethnic population of 98,840, or 4.2 percent of the region's population. Today, 102,517 Kyrgyz live in the region, of which 110 are involved in the national-cultural center. The Kyrgyz population is more numerous in the districts of Andijan region bordering the Kyrgyz Republic, in particular, Kurgantera, Marhamat, Jalal-Abad, Khojaabad, as well as Shahrihan districts.

DISCUSSION

The Korean National Cultural Center was established in 1992 and was registered by the Department of Justice on November 11, 1997 with Certificate No. 45. The population of Koreans in Andijan region is 1465 people, which is 0.06% of the total population of the region. The Noindan Veterans Club has been established at the Korean National Cultural Center, which is made up of senior labor veterans. The activists of the club are well organized to teach young

people the Korean national culture, traditions and values. The Korean National Cultural Center in the region regularly organizes various cultural events. On September 20, 2005 at the initiative of the regional branch of the Korean National Cultural Center was held the national holiday "Chusok", dedicated to the beginning of the harvest of the Korean people. Representatives of all national cultural centers of the region were invited to the event. The event also featured songs of different nationalities. The anniversaries of labor veterans of the Korean Diaspora in the region are regularly celebrated.

The Korean National Cultural Center has successfully organized computer literacy and Korean language courses for young people.

In 2005, 2,622 people in the Andijan region were Koreans. By 2017, the population of the Korean diaspora will be 2,979. The population involved in the National Cultural Center is 62 people. The most densely populated area of the Diaspora is the city of Andijan.

The Armenian National Cultural Center of Andijan region was established in 1994 and was registered by the Department of Justice on November 12, 1994 with the certificate No. 16. Andijan region has a population of 774 Armenians, which is 0.03% of the region's population. A number of works are being carried out by the center. Various measures are being taken to preserve the values of the Armenian nation and pass them on to the younger generation. On February 1, 2005, the Armenian National Cultural Center celebrated the ancient Armenian national holiday "Trndez". In order to promote the national holidays and acquaint the general public with the essence of these holidays, the February 11 issue of the newspaper "Andijanskaya Pravda" published an article "Vzveytes kostrami, brachnye uzy." In the same year, the Armenian Cultural Center organized evenings dedicated to the birthdays of Armenian writers and poets Avetik Isanyan and Sero Khanzadyan.

In 2005, a total of 774 people of Armenian descent lived in the region, while in 2017, the population of the Armenian diaspora was 560 people. The number of people involved in the center is 15 people. The most densely populated area of the Diaspora is the city of Andijan.

The Russian National Cultural Center was established in 1998 and was registered by the Department of Justice on July 14, 1998 with Certificate No. 6/183. Andijan region has a population of 12,677 Russians (1998), which is 0.5% of the region's population. The Russian National Cultural Center works to unite the Russian population in the region, to further strengthen friendships with other nationalities, and to preserve and develop Russian national culture.

By 2000, the Russian population was 0.2 percent. The Russian National Cultural Center is actively involved in all events in the region. In addition, the center regularly holds various evenings, meetings and events dedicated to each holiday. In particular, on January 4, 2005 at the Constitution Square in Andijan on the initiative of the Russian National Cultural Center was organized a New Year's holiday for children of Armenian, Korean, Uyghur, Kyrgyz and other nationalities living in the region. On March 21, the center organized a big celebration on the occasion of Navruz. The ensemble "Slavyanka" organized at the cultural center took part in the holiday with their melodies and songs. The book "Na zemle Babura" by Russian-speaking poets, members of the club "Kaplya", established at the Russian National Cultural Center, was published in 1000 copies, and the book was presented.

In 2013, there were 5 Russian and 42 Uzbek-Russian schools in Andijan region. Representatives of different nationalities are guaranteed access to information in their native language, 1 TV and radio program is published in Russian, 5 in Uzbek-Russian, 6 newspapers and 2 magazines in Uzbek-Russian-English.

In 2005, the population of the Russian diaspora was 22,246, and by 2017, their number was 18,987. The population involved in the center is 120 people. The most densely populated area of the Diaspora is the city of Andijan.

The Andijan regional administration constantly supports the activities of national cultural centers. In order to further develop the activities of cultural centers, to further expand the scope of work to strengthen interethnic friendship and solidarity, the House of Friendship was established. Also, the regional branch of the Republican Fund "Tolerance" was established and on November 28, 2005 was registered in the regional Department of Justice under number 295.

Uyghur, Korean, Armenian, Kyrgyz and Russian national cultural centers operate effectively in Andijan region. These centers play an important role in strengthening friendship, peace and tranquility in our country. Representatives of national cultural centers are actively involved in the celebration of Navruz, Independence Day and Constitution Day at a high level in the region.

There are seven national cultural centers in Fergana Province, including Korean, German, Kyrgyz, Jewish, Tatar, Tajik, and Slavic. The Korean National Cultural Center was registered by the Department of Justice on December 28, 1993, with Certificate No. 08. In 1991, the population of the Korean diaspora was 7,939. By 2004, their number was 6,272. In 2016, their number was 5,932.

The German National Cultural Center was registered by the Fergana Regional Department of Justice on October 14, 1995, with Certificate No. 53. In 1991, the German diaspora in the region numbered 1,620 people. In 2004, the population of this ethnic group was 71 people. In particular, 59 people lived in Fergana, 3 in Margilan, 3 in Quvasoy, 3 in Kokand, 2 in Altiyarik district and 1 in Rishtan district. In 2013, the number was 178 in the region.

In 1991, the population of the Kyrgyz diaspora in Fergana region was 47,561. By 2004, their number was 59,095. In 2016, it was 69,793. The Kyrgyz diaspora is concentrated in the cities of Quvasoy, Fergana and Kokand, as well as in Altiyarik, Tashlak, Yazyavan and Rishtan districts.

The Jewish population in the province was 508 in 1991 and 1,587 in 2004. In 2013, it was 1,932. Jews are concentrated in the cities of Kokand, Fergana, and Margilan.

CONCLUSIONS

The population of the Tatar diaspora in Fergana region in 1991 was 27,409. By 2004, that number was 18,252. In 2016, the figure was 2,719. The population of the Tatar diaspora is concentrated in the cities of Fergana, Kokand, Margilan and Quvasoy, as well as in Tashlak, Altiyarik, Uzbekistan, Dangara, Yazyavan and Buvayda districts.

In recent years, new interactions have emerged from a critical point of view in the assessment of established norms of human relations. The growth of such commonalities, in particular, the growing potential of national and universal relations due to the establishment of stable and harmonious relations between different nations and peoples, has a strong impact on the relations, solidarity and mutual understanding of different nationalities in the Fergana Valley.

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